

**LOGICAL-DEDUCTIVE REASONING APPLIED TO LEARNING
MATHEMATICS** DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14212354**Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza**

Professor at the Municipal Department of Education of Cariacica, Cariacica (ES). Master's student at the Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS), Asunción (PY). E-mail: renatapaz76@hotmail.com.

Renata Mônica Pacheco Nichio

Researcher. Scientific Consultant. Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS). Asunción (PY). Email: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This article addresses the topic of logical-deductive reasoning applied to learning mathematics. This is a subject of utmost relevance, highlighting that the role of this discipline in the educational curriculum is to provide empirical knowledge on how to apply intelligence to challenging everyday situations. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it discusses didactic and methodological techniques aimed at empirical learning of mathematics, using mnemonic resources. Its social relevance lies in the fact that, through this learning method, students can expand their views of the conscious world and beyond. This is a bibliographical research work, based on authors working in the field of education. The general objective is to discuss, academically, how the application of logical-deductive reasoning can help in learning mathematical content, strengthening reason and understanding of curricular didactic processes. All human life is permeated and crossed by mathematical situations, whether they are simple or complex and, in the case of the first, through logical reasoning, one is able to solve them, while in the second, it is necessary support of other materials, such as paper, pens, calculating machines, in addition to a greater time burden. What is intended by solving the problem is not its solution, per se, the didactic interest is to make the student think about the direct and indirect consequences arising from its existence and its resolution; how all this applies to your life and your existence.

Keywords: Logic; Logical-deductive reasoning; Mathematics Learning.

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is part of human existence, in all its dimensions, ranging from a simple act of randomly asking about product prices to large-scale commercial transactions. Interest,

fractions, monetary values, the making of bread, cakes, cookies, meals ; everything passes through mathematical knowledge, in some way and even through its language: half, third part, quarter part, percentage, etc.

In the wake of this, when we observe the major changes that have been taking place in society, we can see that such changes are directly linked to education, teaching and learning. Knowledge is seen as a basis for the creation of wealth, requiring changes in educational models, since the activities developed do not correspond to the challenges that the current world has posed as necessary for social advancement and economic progress (Pienta, 2014).

Specifically, in relation to the undergraduate course in Mathematics, where, combined with the learning that makes up the subject, *strictu sensu* , with its specific disciplines, there is the sum of disciplines that permeate the field of Pedagogy and Didactics, that is, much more than presenting technical mastery, the professional licensed in this field must have broad mastery of didactic knowledge, through which one can create learning strategies, expanding the field of understanding about the subject itself and its applicability in everyday life, having an interest in solving simple and complex problems, stimulating creativity and intelligence.

In this work, which takes the learning of Mathematics as an objective to be achieved by everyone, without distinction, breaking paradigms of common sense, that the subject is very difficult, even going so far as to say that it is impossible to learn it to the point of having full mastery; what we propose to discuss is that at the basis of learning Mathematics is the need to master the capacity for interpretation, considering that it is a science of logic, deductive, which requires detailed exploration of data until it approaches a factual condition, which is interpreted as an indisputable result, because it is exact and, by this expression, it is understood, subjected to rigorous analytical examination.

The directional object of this work was the proposal to discuss the teaching and learning of Mathematics based on everyday experiences, taking as *a leitmotif* the guarantee that all human life is permeated and crossed by mathematical situations, whether they are simple or complex and, in the case of the former, through logical reasoning, one is able to solve them, while the latter requires support from other materials, such as paper, pens, calculators, in addition to a greater amount of time.

Learning Mathematics is a challenge and this is very interesting to experience in the classroom, because the demands that arise go beyond knowing the subject and mastering the content. Starting with the fact that the implementation of the subject in the official curriculum of formal education was linked to the idea of stimulating logical reasoning and, more deeply, to strengthening the practice of deduction, in which the student, when faced with a mathematical

problem, must think of its possible solution, developing hypotheses, in such a way that ways to solve it are thought of.

From this, what emerges is the need to apply actions that induce students to learn, before the discipline, about how to develop and apply abstract reasoning to situations to which mathematical formulas are applied, in order to find logical solutions that respond to desires.

There has been much discussion about methods and strategies for teaching mathematics, and in the midst of all this, it has been forgotten that the main goal of education is not teaching, but rather learning, because this is processed and persists throughout human existence; therefore, the interest lies with the student, so that he or she knows how to direct his or her skills toward this end, even without the help of his or her teachers, enhancing his or her autonomous ability to think and create, that is, to apply his or her intelligence to the interpretation and resolution of problems, quickly and effectively.

Logical reasoning is therefore linked to concepts capable of organizing and clarifying everyday situations, preparing Mathematics students and their variants for more complex circumstances, because this discipline, when taught through the imposition of formulas, repetitive exercises and limited concepts, hinders learning, generating passive, uninterested students with reduced creative power. Logical reasoning requires awareness and the ability to organize thought (Lascano, Homsy, Monteiro, 2019).

In order for teachers to implement this practice in their classes, they must use a variety of strategies, highlighting the need to make students think of different solutions to solve mathematical problems, in addition to the formulas they already know. What matters is the development of logical thinking, which is applied to the situation itself, based on the assumption that each situation is unique and unrepeatable. In other words, it is no use knowing the content, mastering it or solving the problems; one must know how, when and why to solve them and what answers to expect from such action, where each of them applies to everyday situations.

The interest in learning mathematics using logical-deductive reasoning is to prepare the student for action in society, to show themselves capable of solving problems beyond mathematics, when faced with challenges that require the ability to make quick and objective inferences.

LOGICAL-DEDUCTIVE REASONING APPLIED TO LEARNING MATHEMATICS

This article describes the use of logical-deductive reasoning in order to improve the learning of mathematics by students in basic education. Therefore, it is necessary to use reason

in an abstract way to solve problems and learn, that is, seeking mechanisms that help explain and present paths that indicate knowledge of cause and effect and that prove to be simple, because these learning situations need to be recorded and fixed in memory for use and consultation in later situations. At no time should one be led by the naive idea that *simplicity* is equivalent to superficial thinking and shallow solutions. “ Since their inception, both the teaching and learning of Mathematics have been linked to a pragmatic action, to a useful social purpose, especially for society, because the works were intended for the well-being of society, the safety of the population and to generate benefits for all” (Souza and Mário, 2020, pp. 10-1).

In the deductive method , the argument is made from a general premise towards another, particular or singular. The conclusions found in this method were already in the premises analyzed previously and, therefore, it does not produce new knowledge. However, what matters here is not the acquisition of new knowledge, but rather the ability to understand and innovate based on what is already available.

Machado (2000, p. 58) states that “logic deals with forms of argumentation, the ways of linking our reasoning to justify, based on basic facts, our conclusions. Logic is concerned with what can or cannot be concluded from certain information.”

In the case of mathematical learning, there is a given problem that requires a solution and, for this purpose, formulas and concepts are available; but which of these best applies to the explanation of the case? The aim of solving the problem is not its solution, per se, but to lead the student to think about the direct and indirect consequences arising from its existence and its resolution. For example, when solving the equation of the *Pythagorean Theorem* , when finding the value of the hypotenuse, is the question over and the one who solved it deserves applause and praise? The answer is yes; however, this student, or the entire class, must be led to reason about the empirical application of this concept: where is it represented in everyday life? This is because, otherwise, there is learning for the sake of learning, the objective of which is to get a good grade on the test and be approved for the following year, with the nickname of *intelligent*.

Logical Mathematical Reasoning is understood as the organization of thought for coherent decision-making, that is, solving a problem according to the analysis of the arguments presented, to encourage and arouse interest in the contents that are beyond it and that are not represented (Guimarães, 2021). “ They can be developed through the use of methodological, didactic-pedagogical resources and also teaching and learning objects in a technical and/or scientific way” (Pietro, 2018, p. 54).

Thus, learning mathematics and its contents is something that goes beyond all the limits of the traditional methodology that is maintained in schools. The use of logical reasoning aims to bring the student closer to their extra-class reality, precisely because,

Mathematical logical reasoning is the consequence of analyzing data from a given problem, considering its particularities and considering right and wrong as options until reaching a conclusion through the analysis of arguments. After organizing thoughts and arguments, a logical and correct decision-making is expected (Guimarães, 2021, pp. 20-1).

What draws attention, from the above statement, is that, after the decision has been made regarding the supposedly logical and correct answer, there is the opportunity to submit the question for evaluation and determine the degree of accuracy and which elements were decisive for success and which contributed to failure.

We are not trying to make people learn through infallible methods; the idea is to provide advances in the development of critical and creative thinking. “As Mathematics teachers know that the methodical teaching of this subject is intended to improve abstract intellect, they must start from this point to teach it and not just show how to find the right answer or solve the equation” (Souza and Mário, 2020, p. 22).

If this were the case, all the efforts to develop mnemonic capacity and means of mobilizing knowledge would become useless, and it would be enough for the student to have at his disposal a notebook containing all the formulas determined for each case in question that was presented to him. Abstraction would be nothing more than a whim, and education goes beyond all this, taking as a way of understanding it that its intention is the formation of a pragmatic individual.

In official pedagogical guidance documents, the authors follow the following Cartesian logic:

A range of practical actions are put forward that children must learn to develop, but it continues to maintain too great a distance from the teaching and learning process that aims to bring the student closer to the ability to think about the logical sequence of constructing abstract reasoning, something that they will not be able to develop alone, not because of incapacity, but because this requires a special type of training and understanding of complex processes that are completely beyond the reach and mastery of children in the initial grades, but which, once they are already proposed to work on them, pave the way for a long path that leads to the end, to a clearer and more objective understanding of how connections occur at the brain level and outside the conscious world (Souza and Mário, 2020, p. 22).

The use of logical reasoning and its application in learning mathematics aims to develop the ability to think beyond the problem itself and not in it, in itself, which makes it perceptible from a logic that permeates existence. The classroom and all its apparatus, with teacher, methods, strategies and teaching artifacts, represent a very small space and distant from the objective reality in which the student is inserted in his daily life. Hence the need to broaden the understanding about and based on the problems that permeate the lives of students.

Mathematics is often considered an extremely difficult subject. For many, it is even incomprehensible, since it is a subject that deals with formulas and abstract theories (Furtana, 2009). In fact, the problem linked to this supposed difficulty, which has become commonplace, is due to the fact that teachers increasingly distance students from everyday situations that could serve as a foundation for learning Mathematics and its disciplines.

Thus, the learning of mathematics, categorically subjected to theoretical and abstract examples, suffers a negative influence, since, for students, the subject appears as something difficult to understand and of little use.

Vitti argues that,

The failure of mathematics teaching and the difficulties that students present in relation to this subject is not a new fact, as several educators have already listed elements that contribute to the teaching of mathematics being assimilated more as a failure than as a success (Vitti, 1999, p. 19).

There are several aspects that can make learning mathematics difficult, such as teaching outside of context, strictly theoretical classes, which become very tiring, home-school relationships and, most of the time, more work than satisfaction.

Learning in the school environment should make the student understand the subject through experiential situations related to the context in which he/she is inserted, so that in the future, he/she can solve complex problems, since the student learns to attribute meaning to concepts, enabling him/her to make confident and autonomous decisions in different challenging situations.

Students encounter various situations that enable mathematical learning every day; however, they fail to perceive the amount of mathematical information that exists in their daily lives. Therefore, it is the educator's responsibility to guide students' attention to the presence of numbers and fractions in these everyday situations; because, when dealing with a subject with ease, the content studied is assimilated in a more forceful manner, making it possible to access it on future occasions. In addition, the consistent application of group challenges, around

problem-solving, can generate more organization, promote teamwork and improve logical reasoning skills (Ortega, 2019, p. 3).

Solving problem situations related to and based on conditions related to Mathematics is a way to help build concepts, procedures and attitudes about Mathematics, in addition to promoting experiences on the subject itself. Through problems that insert the need for knowledge and mastery of mathematical processes, such challenging situations always present some difficulty and, therefore, stimulate the search for solutions, creativity, resulting in the production of knowledge. According to Dante (2003), problem situations are application problems that portray real everyday situations and that require the use of Mathematics to be solved.

When studying mathematics, using problem-solving as a didactic parameter, students learn to determine the answers to different questions, whether at school or in everyday life. When solving a given problem situation, it is necessary to understand the mathematical concepts before using them; therefore, it can be said that the difficulties encountered are not in the discipline of mathematics, but interdisciplinary difficulties. There are many factors that cause students to hesitate in understanding articles or problems, the most prominent being the lack of interpretation; therefore, “reading should be encouraged and used extensively to achieve satisfactory results in solving problem situations” (Carvalho and Costa, 2018, p. 19).

The student must understand the problem as such and, without a deep and analytical reading, ends up not understanding the dimension that is required of his thinking nor which formulas he should search for in his memory in order to solve the issue.

THE CONFLICT BETWEEN TEACHING AND LEARNING MATHEMATICS

What draws the most attention in teaching is the paradox that exists between the dissemination of ideas aimed at the use of tools and strategies that provide and enhance the development of logical-deductive thinking in the learning of Mathematics and the maintenance of traditional and archaic methods of teaching the subject, using textbooks, the blackboard and problem-solving as the ultimate goal of learning.

When it was discussed that logical reasoning is a strategic tool that aims at the pragmatism of mathematical learning, the idea is to lead the student to correlate what he learns in the classroom with what he experiences in his daily life and that, in a direct way, crosses and challenges him, demanding practical, quick and effective solutions, without any link to later situations.

Thus, what is intended with this type of learning is the expansion of creativity, which should be interpreted as the expression of intelligence, when applied to a given problem situation and, when the teacher presents a challenge, a whole discussion about it should be carried out, in such a way that the points that determine it are clarified, allowing the advancement of logical thinking.

This is not what has been seen in classrooms, where the short and defined time for bureaucratic issues ends up strangling pedagogical practice and what could be expanded through practical classes and challenges that can be practiced is lost, generating adverse reactions from students, such as disinterest and learning based on the law of minimum effort.

Problems are not highlighted in order to be questioned, analyzed and interpreted; they are given and those who manage to solve them are congratulated, and those who cannot solve them copy the answer from the board, without knowing what the whole process means. This does not mean that those who solve them have learned the logical sequence of thought applied in the process; they have simply solved the question and this is the guarantee that they know. No evaluation mechanism is applied, *a posteriori*, in order to determine the extent of the methodology and its potential for logical-deductive learning of the challenges.

Thus, throughout this work we sought to clarify that learning mathematics using the logical-deductive method requires much more than intelligence from the student; he needs to think of formulas, methods and possible solutions for the same problem, considering that the ultimate goal is to increase his capacity to understand and infer life situations.

If the teacher does not understand this didactic situation, all the effort to develop what is called *meaningful learning* will be lost in the midst of *pseudo-learning*, in which the signifiers cease to express any meaning to the student. Logic and deduction can only be achieved through the expression of thought, which results in creativity and the overcoming of learning difficulties that, at each educational level, tend to present themselves in the form of new challenges.

In training courses, there is much emphasis on stimulating students' intelligence through challenges; however, all of this comes up against the factor of class time dedicated to empirical activities, experiments and discussion of the results achieved. This creates a false idea that students are not interested in the subject, or that mathematics is very difficult, when what prevents or hinders its absorption, understanding and mastery is the lack of greater dedication to the problem linked to the methodology used in the teaching and learning processes.

TEACHING AND LEARNING MATHEMATICS FROM EVERYDAY SITUATIONS

Learning mathematical content is always a challenge for teachers and the entire teaching team at school, and is often the target of criticism from both students and teachers, who consider the content extremely difficult and blame it for the high rates of below-average grades and, in the same proportion, for failures.

This is a responsibility that does not fall to Mathematics, considering that it is a science and also a tool; considering the need to offer students a real sense of what they are learning, why they are doing it and why they are doing it, it is pertinent to find ways to develop in students the ability to read and interpret the domain of Mathematics. In contrast, “the divorce between thought and direct experience deprives the former of any real content and transforms it into an empty shell of meaningless symbols” (Adler, 1970, p. 10).

What the author presents is that the real, everyday situation is marked by a very deep range of challenges that allow the student to feel useful and, in the same proportion, to perceive how useful everything that is offered to him in the classroom is, demanding a very broad intellectual effort from him and directed towards a specific end.

In this sense, Zuffi and Onuchic (2007) argue that,

When applying metacognition in the problem-solving process, reference is made to the conscious knowledge that the solver has about the specificity of this process and the deliberate self-regulation that he has in it, taking into account the factors that condition the problem situation, planning his actions and executing and evaluating the results. (Ibidem, p. 86)

The only way to learn something efficiently is through experience. The student needs to come into contact with real situations and know that, even if they are examples, his entire life is filled with whole numbers that are broken down as he moves forward. towards your goals.

It is not just about negotiation situations involving goods and money; it is personal commitments that are marked by the clock, which divides the day into 24 equal parts and these, in turn, into 60 other finite parts, forcing the human being to adapt to it, under an intense dictatorial regime, to which he cannot deny the strictest obedience.

In this line of reasoning, the Mathematics teacher needs to develop and execute his/her praxis, building, from everyday challenges, a special type of mathematical literacy, in which the formulas, language and interest in the content are formed and consolidated until they are structured in such a way that the following stages of teaching and learning the subject are

inherent results of the student's intellectual effort, providing conditions for creativity in problem-solving.

It should be taken into account that Mathematics, as a discipline, has the same duty to collaborate in the formation of the individual as all others. However,

Mathematics in the school context has been a feared and sometimes unimportant subject for students because it does not demonstrate contextualization with everyday life. Thus, it needs to assume its true role in teaching, providing meaningful, creative, practical and contextualized teaching and learning according to the social reality of the student. In their daily lives outside of school, students do mathematics without a reflective attitude, that is, only linked to real needs. In their daily lives, they develop notions of geometry by drawing and dividing flowerbeds; they do statistics and calculus by counting and separating seeds; they deal with finances by establishing prices for production. They perform operations with volume and proportion when stipulating amounts of fertilizer. They observe regularities in the growth and shape of plants and do everything in their own way, with their own language and little formality, without realizing that they are articulating theory and practice (Santos and Lima, 2012, p. 01-2).

Within this context, the role of the Mathematics teacher becomes extremely important, as he/she will have the obligation to motivate students to learn and understand a subject that is not well regarded by the clientele. And not only this, but also to promote the technical-scientific-social enrichment of students with a view to forming their personality with the purpose of exercising their citizenship and preparing them for the formal job market and for life (Souza, 2015).

In this regard,

Mathematics teaching will make its contribution as methodologies are explored that prioritize the creation of strategies, proof, justification, argumentation, critical thinking and favor creativity, collective work, personal initiative and autonomy resulting from the development of confidence in one's own ability to know and face challenges (Brasil, 1997, p. 31).

What is discussed in this work is the need to reconcile theory and practice in the learning of Mathematics, because the student, when faced with a challenging problem, tends to talk to it, in the expectation that it will reveal its secrets, a situation described by LS Vygotsky (1896-1934) as inherent to the act of learning, assimilating, accommodating and synthesizing solutions.

The level of learning increases when such conditions of pedagogical praxis are combined, because it goes beyond the dull situation of *having to learn to get a grade and pass the year* and moves into the dimension of knowledge that becomes useful, necessary and promotes progress towards individual and collective improvement.

CONCLUSION

Something needs to be developed to improve the issue of learning mathematical content and, what can be seen is that there is a long way to go on this topic, because the problem has intensified at the foundations of education, where little reading and the change in disciplinary assessment methods have created a culture that does not strive for mastery of the technique itself; leaving only the interest in memorizing formulas or resorting to technological artifacts that provide immediate answers.

When we think about learning mathematics using logical-deductive resources and methods, the interest lies in the condition of strengthening the mnemonic bases in which, when faced with problem situations that challenge logic, the individual knows how to make connections and create solutions to the challenge that is presented to him. In this sense, learning mathematics ceases to be an end in itself and becomes a means-activity, a task that enhances the brain and its thought structures, generating new connections, increasing intelligence and the way in which it understands situations.

In the opportunities that arise, challenges and proposed solutions are presented to students, using games and questions, and what is perceived is that there is and persists a veiled [*and revealed*] fear of presenting an answer that does not match the problem and ending up being punished by the teacher and colleagues. Situations of attempts to solve a given problem must be planned in such a way that the ideas presented can be tested, even if they immediately appear to be unrealistic, because when empirically testing a proposal, there is a rare opportunity to measure its scope and how close or far it is from the object in question.

Learning mathematics using logical-deductive reasoning techniques is a didactic field to be explored and which still requires in-depth and systematic study, as well as adaptation of the formal educational model that prevails in Brazilian public schools, which are concerned with raising scores in the IDEB tests.

The experience represents, in itself, a challenge and, together, there is the analysis of the school-PPP-teaching-learning set, which in order to understand this entire dimension and reach a synthesis leads to adverse deductions about what the classroom is and the entire proposed result, through didactic planning.

One of the most challenging aspects in the field of learning Mathematics is the contrast between the discourse of integration that is preached and the cold, distant reality, devoid of a causal link with reality, that the teacher's pedagogical practice presents and its results, which are not at all encouraging.

Among the situations that attract attention, the fact that teachers report that they provide learning conditions through playful activities stands out; but when challenging questions are posed to students, they do not know anything; they do not develop thinking and creativity in solving problems. Like everyone else, they confuse playfulness with boring games and games used to overcome boredom in the classroom.

As for the role of the teacher, even if it was a simulation, because it took place through formal and informal dialogue with the teachers and members of the school's pedagogical team, what we can see is that mathematics education continues without a direction, without a methodology that presents objective results, and the solution is to continue justifying the students' failure in learning it, as being the fault of the difficulty in teaching and learning the subject.

When observing the classes, one realizes that the examples used are situations that are outside the empirical scope of the students and, for this reason, they move away from the interest in learning how Mathematics and its various functions apply to functional reality. When preparing the classes, the material that one has access to is a primer prepared by a bureaucrat, who does not even have a degree in Mathematics; a textbook written by someone who does not work as a teacher in Basic Education and, the result is the historical state of the subject: low grades, poor learning and, failure!

All of this, to a great extent, leads to a deep reflection on the role of Mathematics and the teacher of the subject, understanding that there is a pressing need to create methodologies that encourage the careful and coordinated learning of the subject.

Through the research and the authors explored, the horizon of perception about the subject and the conditions it reveals was broadened, offering opportunities to seek new perspectives in the field of teaching and learning Mathematics, producing a teaching practice that awakens the student to understand the mathematical universe that surrounds him and how he can, based on everyday situations, develop his intellect, expand his intelligence and create new forms of analysis, interpretation and synthesis in relation to Mathematics and its theoretical and empirical aspects. It is not possible to maintain the stance of a subject that is difficult to learn and end the entire discourse with this jargon, as if it represented the whole truth about it. What is clear is that there is a lack of a teaching method appropriate to the subject that combines effective learning.

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